

A Model of Catholicity for Catholic Schools

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Abstract - Using qualitative and quantitative methods, this study was designed to establish a model of the Catholicity of Catholic Basic schools in Davao Provinces, Philippines. The outputs of focus group discussions were analysed and used to construct the framework of the study and the basis for the survey instrument. The data gathered were subjected to Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) which produced four factors on Catholicity and seven factors for External Factors. The identified factors were loaded into the proposed model and analyzed using Structural Equation Model (SEM). The findings revealed a significant influence of the External Factors to Catholicity affirming the study's theoretical foundation. All seven observed variables showed positive contribution to External Factors (Latent Variable). Moreover, the findings showed significant contributions of the four observed variables to Catholicity (Latent Variable). Thus, the model measures *Catholicity* looking at the four observed variables and is further influenced by *External Factors* measured in terms of the seven observed variables. Based on the SEM findings which were supported by related literature and studies, the model of the Catholicity of Catholic Basic Education Schools in Davao Provinces will help schools remain faithful to their identity and mission as Catholic institutions.

Keywords - Basic Education, Catholic Culture, Catholicity, Structural Equation Model, Digos City, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

The present situation of which Catholic schools are confronted is critical. Aside from striving to cope with the demands of sustaining and enhancing quality education, Catholic schools face enormous challenges as reflected on the kind of graduates they are producing. In July of this year, the Vatican stripped Pontifical Catholic University of Peru of its Catholic title. The Vatican said that the Peruvian University has drifted away from its Catholic foundation (The Associated Press, 2012). In his first visit to Rome's Sacred Heart Catholic University, Pope Benedict XVI posed question, referring to the students in Catholic universities, "What culture did they find, assimilate, and develop?" (Catholic News Agency, 2005). The Pontiff must have been alarmed by the devastation to the faith done by millions of Catholic students.

A 2003 study in America revealed that students in many Catholic colleges have significant opposition to the teachings of the Church. This was affirmed by another study which concluded that many American Catholic colleges do not comply with the *Ex Corde Ecclesia*, the 1990 Vatican constitution that provides guidelines and requirements for Catholic college and universities throughout the world (The Cardinal Newman Society, 2012). Some of the American colleges and universities were under fire like the so called Notre Dame scandal wherein the university invited and honored Barack Obama who was a staunch advocate of what the Church considers as anti-life. For the past years and especially this year, the Philippine Church has been on the fighting mode against the passing of the Republic Health Bill. This is the same threats the American colleges and universities are facing (The Cardinal Newman Society, 2012).

On the other hand, Catholic schools continued to be challenged as to their graduates when they are already in power. Even Msgr. Fernando Capalla, DD, former chairperson of the Catholic Bishops Conference in the Philippines (CBCP), once said: "It is very discouraging to note that most of the lawmakers who are products of Catholic schools are the ones who are making bills that are detrimental to the moral values

of the spirit" (Ventura, 2005). In his work with a Non Government Organization "Ehem!", Alejo (2008), discovered that many of the corrupt officials in the Philippines are graduates of Catholic schools. Moreover, there is a concern based on the result of a study in 200 which predicted that the Philippines would lose its status as a Catholic country in 40 years. That is if the trend continues, recalled Fr. Catlino Arevalo (as cited by Sauler, 2012). This is a big challenge for the Catholic school in the Philippines as the country commemorates 400 years of Catholic education in 2012.

Considering all these realities, Catholic schools must reflect on these questions. How can they remain faithful to their identity as Catholic? In what way, amidst the growing secularism, can they be responsive and relevant to society as the educational arm of the Catholic Church? Since Catholic schools are institutions or organizations, Catholicity is also thought to be affected by internal and external factors in the organization. Johnson and Fauske (2005) argued that those activities in educational organizations, such as leading, teaching, learning, counselling, coaching, among others, take place in an organizational context. Thus, looking at the Catholicity of Catholic schools, there's a need to approach it from the organizational perspective.

While the basic intention of this study was developing a model, this is also useful in evaluating the Catholicity of Catholic schools from the organizational perspective. This study was anchored on the theory of Lusthaus, Adrien, Anderson, Carden and Montalvan (2002). They argued on the presence of certain contextual forces which are engines for organizational performance. These are organizational capacity, forces in its external environment and internal motivation. Since Catholic schools are also organizations, it is assumed that contextual factors identified by Lusthaus et. al. (2002) are also drivers for their performance. Since this study was about the Catholicity of Catholic schools, theological reflections and organizational theories were used to provide a strong foundation.

In terms of Catholicity, theological reflections provide a solid foundation. First, Christology provides the basis of the Catholicity of Catholic schools in the person of Jesus. The Church traces its mystery, foundation and life (Ecclesiology) in Jesus and is mandated to continue His mission (Missiology). As a Catholic institution, a Catholic school

is part of the Church. Being part of the Church, it responds to the missionary mandate of the latter. In particular, a Catholic school is doing one of the missionary activities of the Church, i.e. Christian education.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Having established the theoretical and theological foundations, this study was conceptualized to develop a model of Catholicity for Catholic schools in the Davao Provinces.

METHODOLOGY

A combination of qualitative and quantitative methods of research was used. The qualitative method was utilized in generating internal and external factors on the Catholicity of Catholic schools through focus group discussions (FGDs). The first batch FGD was participated in by school administrators and representatives. It produced 49 internal and external factors of Catholicity. These factors were used to propose a framework of the study. Another batch of FGDs was conducted participated in by administrators. The result was the affirmation of the identified factors during the first batch of FGDs and more factors were added. The outputs were analysed and used to construct the framework of the study and became the basis for the survey instrument. Selected students, teachers, non-teaching personnel, administrators and parents of the Basic Education Schools in Davao Provinces participated in the study by answering the survey instrument.

The quantitative method was employed to analyse and interpret the data from the survey using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). The theoretical concept in factor analysis is to look at the relationship of the surface attributes to internal attributes (Williams, Osman & Brown, 2010). The factors extracted from EFA were loaded to a proposed model using Structural Equation Model (SEM) technique. Path Analysis, using the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), evaluated the assumed causation among a set of dependent and independent constructs (Martin, 2011).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the initial analysis, the data were subjected to Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). After satisfying the sampling adequacy requirement using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure (KMO) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, Catell's scree test and Kaiser's criterion or the eigenvalue rule were employed before the factors were rotated using the Orthogonal Varimax Rotation. This analysis produced four *factors* (observed variables) on *Catholicity* (latent variable). These factors were (1) Faithfulness to the Mission of the Church and Christ-centeredness, (2) Culture, (3) Witnessing of the Members of the School Community and (4) Extension Service. The EFA also generated seven *factors* (*observed variables*) for the latent variable *External Factors* consisting of (1) Academic and Spiritual Programs, (2) Socio-cultural, (3) Leadership and Motivation, (4) Stakeholders, (5) Collaboration with the local church, (6) Mass Media and (7) Economic-Political. Interestingly, the factor groupings, which yielded higher correlation coefficients and loaded to Factors, essentially affirmed the factors identified through the FGDs.

The identified factors were loaded into the proposed model using SEM technique. The model was composed of two latent variables namely, Catholicity and External Factors. Catholicity has four observed variables and External Factors has seven observed variables. Examining the Notes for Model section, the data revealed that there were no errors or warnings. This suggested that it was already safe to continue with further analysis. However, the Chi-square value of 126.72 with 43 degrees of freedom, returning a probability value of less than .000 suggested that the model *did not fit* the data because of its significant value. In other words, with this chi-square value the null hypothesis was rejected. That was not a good result because the ultimate goal using SEM is actually not to reject the null hypothesis so that the model fits the data. This unusual consideration of the non-significant Chi-square is based on the assumption that Chi-square is sensitive to model sample size and normality (Siu Loon HOE, 2008). The unfavorable result in terms of the goodness of fit of the model was confirmed by Tucker-Lewis Index (*TLI*) .922 and Comparative Fit Index (*CFI*) .939 Values which were lower than the accepted value of

.95 or higher. Similarly, the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (*RMSEA*) value was .057 which was higher than the accepted value of .05 or below.

Modifying the Model to Obtain Superior Goodness of Fit

In using SEM, it is very seldom that one achieves a model fit in the first try. Thus, a model modification is advised (Guo, Perron & Gillespie, 2008). This is also called model re-specification. Looking at the modification indices it was found out that correlating the residuals e_6 and e_5 substantially reduced the chi-square. Thus, a model was respecified by doing the aforementioned process (Please refer to the double-headed arrow between e_6 & e_5 in Figure 1).

The new model produced the Chi-square value of 90.74 and the degrees of freedom of 42. While the p-value of .000 was significant and did not support the claim of the goodness of fit, other indices confirmed the model fit. In particular, the TLI .953 and CFI .964 Values were beyond the accepted .95. This means that the respecified model satisfied the criterion of the goodness of fit of the model. This was further supported by the *RMSEA* value of .04 which was lower than the cut-off value of .05 or below.

Standardized Regression Path Diagram

Figure 1 shows the path diagram of the model with the Structure Coefficients, Squared Multiple Coefficients and Correlation Coefficient. The Structure Coefficients are the standardized regression coefficients which are linked with each path. Like in interpreting regression coefficients, these values refer to the amount of change in Y given a standard deviation unit change in X.

Figure 1: Correlation, structure coefficients & squared multiple coefficients of the model

Figure 1 reveals a significant influence of the External Factors (.55) to Catholicity, thus, affirming the study’s theoretical foundation. All seven observed variables also showed positive contribution to the latent variable External Factors. Collaboration with the local church (.73) and Stakeholders (.73) were tied to have the greatest contributions. These were followed by Leadership and Motivation (.61), Academic and Spiritual Programs (.43), Socio-cultural (.42), Mass Media (.37) and Economic-Political (.34).

Moreover, the findings showed significant contributions of the four observed variables to the latent variable Catholicity. Culture (.79) showed having the greatest influence followed by Witnessing of the Members of the School Community (.63), Extension Service (.58) and Faithfulness to the Mission of the Church and Christ-centeredness

(.57).

Thus, the model measures *Catholicity* by looking at the four observed variables and is further influenced by *External Factors* measured in terms of the seven observed variables.

The findings on the contributions of the identified observed variables to Catholicity affirmed the solid grounding on the basic components of the Catholic schools that make them truly Catholic. Popes John Paul II and Benedict XVI reiterated this centrality of Christ in the life of a Catholic school in their speeches and documents (O'Connell, 2009; Wuerl, 2006). It is Christ who is the reason why Catholic schools bring about the vision of Christianity in everything they do and contribute (Curran (2001).

The significant contribution of Culture was supported by an organizational theory. For instance, a strong contribution of Culture to Catholicity is what Alfuah (2004) called the best model for a successful organization. The findings were also supported by the study of Clark (2005) which tried to explore Catholic school identity in terms of the school culture which for him gives strong evidence that the school is Catholic.

In terms of Extension Service, Catholic schools were known for serving beyond the confines of school campuses. The positive contribution of this factor marked the Catholic schools' fidelity to Jesus' commandment of love- that is love of God and love of neighbor. This was the concrete manifestation of the schools' mission which is not only restricted within the four walls of the classrooms. Example of this was supported by Limbani (2005) who singled out the schools' concern for the poor as part of the Catholic schools' mission and Catholic identity. The documents of the Church, particularly *Lumen Gentium* and *Gaudium et Spes*, called the people of God to participate in the mission particularly in helping the least in the society. In fact, the Church in the Philippines had specifically mentioned the poor as her main concern as exemplified by how she is described as the "Church of the Poor" (Bacani, 2005).

On the aspect of Christian witnessing, the study confirmed what Pope Paul VI emphasized on the primacy of witnessing over preaching as the best strategy for evangelization. This was an echo to what St. James said, "Faith without action is dead" (James 2:26, *The New American*

Bible). A school can only attest itself as truly Catholic if its members practice what they believe (Pope Paul II, 1990) while at the same time work for the integral formation of the students (Grocholewski, 2009), the unique contribution of Catholic education.

As to the contribution of External Factors, several studies and literature supported the findings of the present study. For example, the positive contribution of Academic and Spiritual Programs in this study, which has several components or themes under it, substantiated the earlier pronouncement of the Congregation of Catholic Education (Laghi & Martins, 1997) which emphasized the importance of the schools' curriculum as the beacon for the integral formation of students. This was also supported by the study of Clark (2005) who hypothesized Catholic school's identity as truly Catholic if there is a strong emphasis on the formation of students which is embedded in the curriculum and instruction.

From the organizational point of view, professional development is a factor considering the economic value of additional or development of knowledge, experience, skills and capacities which are ingredients for organizational success (Daft, 2003). The significant contribution of professional development backed up the assertion of Pope Paul VI in *Gravissimum Educationis* which recognized the need for the teachers' work to accomplish the goals and programs for any Catholic school.

When it comes to Spirituality, which is another component of Academic and Spiritual Programs, its positive contributions to Catholicity was supported by how McBrien (1981) defined it as a way of being religious. Other components of Academic and Spiritual Programs were the vision, mission and school policy. The findings affirmed the study of Clark (2005) who which highlighted mission and policy as the strong evidences as to the identity of Catholic schools.

As to Socio-cultural, the findings corroborated the church's teaching about the family as the "cradle of life and love" (*Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Church*, art 212, 213, 238). Another study conducted by Mullner (2006), which emphasized the strong commitment of the school to make the parents and other stakeholders participate in the school's activities, was reaffirmed by the findings of this study.

On Leadership and Motivation, a study by Slater (2008) on the influence of leadership in Catholic institutions supported the findings of the study. According to Slater, when leaders perform well in their duties, especially acting as spiritual leaders, they influence much in the organizations. Similarly, the positive contribution of leadership to External Factors was substantiated by Wong (2002) and Ruth (2009) on the impact of a leader to the Catholicity of a Catholic school. He found out that a lay leader is influential in guiding the whole institution into growth and refining the school's character and academic niche. In terms of motivation, its positive contribution was supported by a study of Lumpkin (2008) who proposed a roadmap of treating people which literally emphasizes rewards and recognition as one of the most important factors for motivating people to work harder.

The positive contribution of the Stakeholders was supported by Martin (2009) & Greeley (1992). In particular Martin (2009) believed that one of the hallmarks of Catholic schools is parents' high involvement in the school. Greeley (1991) emphasized the need to activate human resources. The findings of the study gave a confirmatory evidence of what the teachings of the Church say. In particular, the Sacred Congregation of Catholic Education remarked that Catholic schools can only become a community of faith if there is sharing of Christian commitment among the members of the school community (Baum & Javiere, 1982). Thus, an environment that nurtures the morals, thinking and feelings of people are specially provided by those who are part of the school community (Ricken, 2009).

As to the Collaboration with the Local Church, its positive contribution was supported by the theological reflection which posited that Catholic schools exist in order to do the mission of the Church (Missiology). In other words the findings of the study re-affirmed the identity of Catholic schools which is tied up with the parish or diocese. The very nature of Catholic schools is closely connected with the Church which is expressed in the schools' commitment to the mission of the Church (Pope John Paul, 1990).

In terms of the contributions of Mass Media (Factor 6) and Economic-Political (Factor 7), the findings of the study corroborated the negative and at the same time positive effects of both to Catholicity.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, supported by related literature and studies, the model is a perfect guide for Catholic schools to remain faithful to their identity. It also provides relevant factors that would assist Catholic schools in responding to the mandates of the church. The model could also serve as the groundwork for policy formulation, strategic planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation for individual Catholic school or Association of Catholic schools. Similarly, the model can be used as the basis for program interventions by other agencies working and collaborating with Catholic schools, such as the Department of Education (DepEd), Commission on Higher Education (CHED), and the local churches. Moreover, the model also sets directions for future researchers to have in-depth study based on the factors included in the model.

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